

Karma Theory and its Appraisal

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Abstract—This electronic document is a “live” template and already defines the components of your paper [title, text, heads, etc.] in its style sheet. ***CRITIC** One of the most disturbing riddles concerning human existence, in particular, and that of all living beings, in general, is the alarming diversity of living conditions and the inevitable presence of evil and suffering in the life of every individual. In different cultural traditions, attempts have been made to solve this riddle by taking the help of various hypotheses like the play-off satan (devil), disobedience of divine ordinance, etc. One of the solutions put forth, and generally accepted in Indian culture, is the Karma theory. The theory of Karma may be called the essential element, not only of moral theories in India but also of popular belief. With the exception of Carvakas, all the Indian philosophical systems accord recognition to Karma theory. The basic assumption of this theory is that as you sow, so shall you reap. One gets the fruit according to his Karma. Here, man's Karma is the 'cause' and the result obtained by him is the 'effect'. Thus, in the field of morality, the theory of karma is treated as a causal law. But what is karma? Can we treat the theory of karma as a theory of causality, and if we can, then what are its basic elements? Who gives the consequences of karma? Is it necessary to accept God as the provider of fruits? Does a man suffer the consequences of his own actions, or do others also have to suffer the consequences of the actions of others? The purpose of my paper is an attempt to understand the theory of karma in the light of the above-mentioned questions, which has, for centuries, exercised an unmitigated and pervasive influence on the mode of thinking and way of living of the people of the Indian sub-continent.

Keywords— Karma, Cause, Effect, Carvaka, Consequences, Philosophy

I. INTRODUCTION

The word 'Karma' has special significance in Indian philosophical tradition. Karma literally means an action. This term is derived from the Sanskrit root 'Kri' which means 'to do or make'. This word has been used in many contexts. In the broad sense, Karma means any act, whether that action has any purpose or not, whether it is moral or outside the scope of morality. In the second sense, Karma means any action which has some moral value or moral significance. Philosophers use this term in this sense. In the third sense, the cumulative result of any work can also be called karma, in this sense, karma can be considered similar to fate. The word karma is also used in the sense of an invisible power. This invisible power creates the destiny of the living being. But if we look more carefully, we will find that all these meanings of the word karma are interrelated. According to Bhagwat Geeta-Gyanam *jneyam parijnata trividha karmachodana, Karanam karma karteti trividha: karma sangrah:* (18/18)[1]. The knower, knowledge and the object of knowledge – these three motivate action. Even

so, the doer, the organs and activity- these are the three constituents of action.

There are three different types of Karma - (a) Sanchita Karma: Sanchita is a Sanskrit word meaning 'piled up' or 'collected', so sanchita karma means 'actions that have accumulated'. Sanchita karma is the totality of all karma accumulated in an individual's past lives, including all good and bad actions. In general, karma has an effect on the current incarnation and will also affect future lives.(b)Prarabdha Karma: Prarabdha means 'commenced' or 'begun', so prarabdha karma translates as 'action that has begun'. Those actions of the past that have started bearing fruit are called Prarabdha karma.(c) Kriyamana Karma: Kriyamana karma is that human beings are creating in the present, the fruits of which will be experienced in the future. The subject of karmic consequences is large, deep and complex. Maharishi Vyas has said- "*Karmagatishchitra Durvignyana Cheti*" (Commentary on Yoga. 2.13)[2]. That is, the pace of action is strange and difficult to know. Still, Karma theory is that the entire universe is governed by the law of cause and effect. The supporters of this theory believe that this law of cause and effect applies not only to the objects of the physical world but also to the thoughts and actions of human beings. According to this rule, whatever man thinks and does in his life inevitably produces some consequences. Like the physical world, nothing happens suddenly or without reason in human life too. Everything that happens in this world has its cause, it never happens by chance. This means that the happiness or sorrow that a person is experiencing in the present is the inevitable result of his past good or bad deeds. No other person is responsible for this. Similarly, whatever happiness or sorrow he receives in future life will also be the result of good or bad deeds of his present life. From this is clear that according to the supporters of Karmaism, the process of actions and their result is governed by the essential law of cause and effect from which no human being can be free. Now the question arises that if a human being is not free from this theory then how much freedom does he have in acting?

II. FUNDAMENTAL ELEMENT OF KARMA THEORY

There are some fundamental elements of karma theory, without which karma theory cannot be possible [3, 4, 5].

A. Rebirth:

The basic characteristic of karmas is that they do not leave the doer until he gets their fruit. Just as a calf can find its mother in a herd of thousands of cows. Your Karmas follows you in every birth you take."Avshaymev Bhoktavyam Krit Karma shubhasubham, Na Bhukatam Kshiyate karma kalpa koti shtairapi"(Brahma Vaivarta

Purana/44/74) We do not get the fruits of our actions immediately. It takes more or less time to get fruits. If it is accepted that at the time of death, there are some deeds whose fruits we have not experienced and after death, the person ceases to exist, then huge moral chaos will spread. A person will be saved from suffering the punishment of some bad deeds while some will be deprived of the beneficial fruits of some other deeds. Therefore, in order to enjoy the fruits of the karma not experienced in this birth, it is necessary for a person to exit even after death and to be born again.

B. Freedom of will:

There are two views in Indian tradition regarding freedom of will. First, the phenomenal self (Jiva) is free to perform action and is dependent on enjoying the fruit. Vedas say that you should wish to live 100 years only while doing good deeds. Nyaya philosophy also refutes the creation of God and proves that man is the doer of the deeds. Maharishi Jaimini has accepted the freedom of the phenomenal self. Swami Dayanand Saraswati has accepted the phenomenal self as the doer of action and God as the arranger of their fruits. But in Shruti and Smriti, vakyas expressing the against opinion are also found. Such Acharyas hold the view that the doer of the deeds is the human being but inspiration to do those deeds comes from destiny or from God. Man is only efficient, he only has the ego of being a doer. The doer is a living being, but God gives the inspiration to do it. The will of the creator (vidhata) and the karma samskara of the previous birth act as an inhibitor (avrodhak) and restrict the freedom of action of the living being. An example from Geeta can be given in this. When Arjun, disillusioned with his duties, refused to fight the war, then Krishna said—*“These warriors stand already slain by Me; be you only an instrument, Arjuna”*. In this context, the example of Mahabharata also can be given. When Duryodhana is asked, why he does this immoral act, his answer seems to be a question mark on the individual’s freedom of action—*“Janami Dharmam na cha me pravritih, Janamayamdharma na cha me Nrvitih”* (I know what is right (dharma), yet I cannot get myself to follow it. I know what is wrong (adharma), yet cannot refrain from it. (it is not my fault) It is as if some unknown force dwells in my heart and impels me to do, what I do). Which of the above two approaches is appropriate? My opinion here is syncretic. It is not right to consider man as completely independent and it is also not right to consider God as the doer. Although karma theory believes that our present life is largely determined and influenced by our prarabdha karma, yet we are free to live our lives as per our wish in the given context. It is necessary that our prarabdha binds us, but it does not bind completely. This situation has been explained very well by Dr. S. Radhakrishnan in his inimitable style [6]. He says— *“We can use the material with which we are endowed to promote our ideals. The cards in the game of life given to us. We do not select them. They are traced to our past Karma, but we can call as we please, lead what suit we will, and as we play, we gain or lose. And there is freedom.”* (*The Hindu View of Life*, p.75) We know that many foolish people lose the game despite getting good cards and some clever people win the game despite getting bad cards. In this way, in the karma theory a person is independent and safe. It is only because of

this freedom that it is possible for a person to be the creator of his own destiny. What we get may be determined by our own prarabdha but what we will do is not predetermined. Thus, in the theory of karma, we see the coordination of determinism and freedom. Karma theory is not only fatalistic, it is also effortful. We are responsible for the fruits obtained by our actions.

C. Existence of permanent self:

The theory of karma holds that we each have an immortal soul, it is different from the body; the body is physical; it is non-physical. The body is destroyed, not the soul. In the ever-changing body, the soul is the only unchangeable element that provides unity and integrity to the personality. This continuous unity of personality is possible not only in this birth but also in thousands and millions of births of individuals because of this unchangeable element, the soul.

D. Subtle body:

One also believes that there is a subtle body inside our physical body. The subtle body is the combination of buddhi, ahankara, the eleven sense-motor organs and the five tanmatra. This subtle body is a carrier of the sanskaras and fruits of karma. At the time of rebirth, this subtle body passes from one body to another along with the soul. This body remains with the soul until it attains salvation. When there will be no karma left to enjoy, then there will be no need for rebirth and the soul will be free from all the bondages of karma and the cycle of birth and death.

III. KARMPHAL VIPAK

The result of karma is achieved only when it is resolved. Just as the potter prepares a pot and cooks it, he purifies it by placing it in the fire. Similarly, when a man performs and action, then the residual desires in his mind play the main role in Karma Vipak. As explained in Brihadaranyaka Upanishad, it has been said that this soul is lustful, it thinks as per its desires, it acts according to what it thinks. Whatever action one performs, the same happens, that is, one gets the result. In this way, the next birth becomes certain by wishing and thinking about the birth. The question may be whether desire or lust comes first. How does the lust of one birth determine the births to come? In response to this, it has been clarified in Brihadaranyaka Upanishad that wherever there is lust, there the soul goes. Mundkoupnishad also tells about this subject that whatever lustful objects a soul desires, its birth becomes certain due to the result of those desires.

IV. WHO GIVES THE FRUITS OF KARMA?

There are two opinions in philosophy regarding who gives the fruits of their karma to living beings. Nyaya philosophy believes that God is the moral ruler of every living being and provides justice and fair fruits to life. Philosophers like Mimamsaka etc [7]. Those who do not accept the intervention of God believe that karma itself gives fruits to life. Theists argue that karma gets destroyed by giving rise to actions. Because action is the opposite of karma. If karma is destroyed then how can it give the fruits that will be received later? [8]. The second argument is that karma is an inanimate element. How can he intelligent and impartial conscious being? Vedanta says that God is the giver of

fruits.

A Karmaist may ask that if God is the giver of fruits then it is ever possible that He may not give fruits as per the deeds? The answer to this question is negative. Because God does not have the power to make a living being do any work and God can stop its results. This means that God is bound to give results. But this is a huge contradiction. One who is capable of giving is also capable of not giving. If He can only give and cannot withhold the fruits, then it means that it is His nature to give fruits. In such a situation, it will give fruits even in the absence of deeds. Because nature is nature, it cannot be changed. It is the nature of the sun to give light. It is never possible for it not to give light. But according to theist, God expects deeds to give. Karmists argue that if God cannot stop the fruits of Karma then it means that the power of karma is greater than the power of God[9]. Karma is more powerful. Therefore, karma itself is capable of giving fruits. Kumaril Bhatt says that the power to produce 'Apoorva'. Although karma is momentary, it leaves a mark on the soul in a unique form. It gives fruit to the doer over time. Karmists even say that keeping records of the place, time quantity and means of the fruits and arranging them is also in the hand of karma. Therefore, Bharthari has considered it more appropriate to worship Karma, leaving aside Gods and the Creator.

"*Falam karmayattam kimmarganai, kinch vidhinaa ,namastkarmabhyo vidhirapi na yebhayah prabhvati*" (*Bhartrhari, Nitishatakam-97*) (Let us salute gods. They too, are under the control of the creator. Then Fate deserves a bow on our hands. But it too, imparts the fruits only of our own actions. Therefore, and what with gods and also what with the creator? A bow to our actions which cannot be overruled even by the creator himself.

The third approach which is developed by Charvaka, is accept that there is no existence of God and Soul but, one gets the reward of his actions. How it is possible? In answer to this question, Charvak says that two types of deeds are seen in the world. One is worldly and the other is supernatural. As for as worldly deeds are concerned, the results of these deeds are determined by the universally accepted king or administrator. We see that the king who is accepted by the who commit prohibited acts like theft etc. By sending them to prison etc. in the form of punishment. Similarly, the king himself awards wealth and honour to the person who does good deeds like saving someone's life etc. As for as supernatural deeds are concerned, no one has witnessed them till dated. Charvakas also rejected the use of supernatural causes to describe natural phenomena. To them all natural phenomena was produced spontaneously from the inherent nature of things. The fire is hot, The water cold, refreshing cool the breeze of morn; By whom come this variety? From their own nature was it born.

V. CONCLUSION

From the above discussion of karma theory, it appears that it is fatalistic to some extent and karmistic to some extent. Birth, age and enjoyment, all these are given to a person by his destiny, but kriyaman karma makes him active. Here question can be asked whether karmaism is dependent on fatalism or fatalism is based on karmaism. Bhishma says in Mahabharata that karma is like a seed and destiny is like the soil. Without seeds, the land cannot

produce crops. Nothing is gained by relying on fate. Whereas everything is achieved by doing karma (Mahabharata, Anushasan Parva 6/6/7/8). The consequences of karma cannot be avoided. It will definitely bear fruit when the time comes. Neither a tree blossoms nor any work is accomplished before time. Therefore, adaptation to time and circumstances is important, not God. If the law of cause and effect is the fact of the physical world then the law of karma is of the moral world. If the karma is not ripe and is accumulated in your account, then it can be burnt by using Sadhana, Bhakti and the methods given by the Guru. But if they are ripe then it is certain to enjoy their fruits. We conclude that while karma theory describes every incident as the result of karma, it also explains the importance of individual freedom. we are the creators of our own future. In this form, we can also wish for the desired results through freedom of will and effort. The song the *Charaiveti Charaiveti* of Aitareya Brahmin proclaims that the good fortune of the one who is sitting also remains sitting, but when someone stands for action, his sleeping good fortune also awakens. Therefore, be active. Karmaism in itself is a holistic principle that makes human life perfect. The entire life is connected through karmaism, the stream of Indian thought because the flow of karma is the flow of life.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The process of writing and the content of the article do not give grounds for raising the issue of a conflict of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The Research is supported by an Incentive Grant under IoE, BHU [Grant No. R/Dev/D/IoE/Incentive Grant (Phase-IV)/2022-23/59812].

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

This article is completely the original work of the author. It has not been published before and will not be sent to other publications until the PRIA editorial board decides not to accept it for publication.

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